

Investigation of Waste Polyethylene Terephthalate Plastic as a Sustainable Supplementary Material for Road Construction

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Abstract: The most common asphalt for road construction is a mixture of aggregates and bitumen. Bitumen is the most expensive of all the materials for asphalt production. This study involved partial replacement of bitumen with pulverised Polyethylene Terephthalate (plastic bottles without caps) in wearing course asphalt production. Waste plastic bottles were purchased from waste plastic vendors, garbage trucks operating at various dump sites in the area. The caps were removed from the plastic bottles. The bottles without cap were cleaned, dried and pulverised. Sizes passing test sieve size 2.36mm were used for the study. Normal asphalt (Asphalt without plastic addition) was designed with the addition of 5%, 5.5%, 6.0%, 6.5%, 7.0% and 7.5% bitumen content and tested by the Marshal method to obtain the Optimum Bitumen Content (OBC) and other Marshal parameters. OBC of 6.4% was deduced from the curves of Stability vs Bitumen Content, Bulk Density vs Bitumen Content and Voids in Total Mix vs Bitumen Content. The OBC was partially replaced by the pulverised Polyethylene Terephthalate at 6%, 8%, 10%, 12% and 14% in the hot asphalt mixture. The Marshal test result for the modified asphalt revealed that only 12% replacement met the local and international requirement for road construction and hence the Optimum Plastic Content (OPC) for Polyethylene Terephthalate asphalt modification. The use of polyethylene terephthalate in the construction and maintenance of roads will contribute to eco-friendly road construction and effective plastic waste management in Nigeria.

Keywords: Bitumen, Polyethylene Terephthalate, Asphalt, Marshal test, Plastic Waste Management, Road Construction.

Introduction

Plastic waste is a global problem. From the depth of the oceans to the tops of mountains, the problem affects ecosystems, wildlife, and even human health (Kalali *et al.*,2023). Little wonder the theme of World Environment Day for the year 2023 and 2025 were Solutions to Plastic Pollution and Beat Plastic Pollution respectively. Nigeria, being one of the most populous countries in Africa, is seriously affected by the global plastic pollution problem. Owerri West L.G.A, in Imo state is not left out because of its urbanization, high population, the widespread and improper disposal of plastic products (Bandara *et al.*, 2023). The area struggle with inadequate waste management infrastructure, lack of recycling facilities, and limited public awareness about the impacts of plastic pollution (Tiamiyu, 2023; Mujtaba *et al.*, 2024). Efforts are being made by the government (State and local) and various non-governmental organizations to address the issue (Kehinde *et al.*,2023; Schroder *et al.*,2023; Ogundare, 2023). However, the scale of the problem remained substantial.

There are also significant concerns about the extent of bad roads in the area and in Nigeria generally (Mosuro *et al.*, 2023). Nigeria, like many developing countries, is faced with

challenges related to the state of its road infrastructure. The country's road network, both in urban and rural areas, suffers from issues such as potholes, lack of maintenance, and inadequate construction. Bad roads in the area have been a cause of accidents, traffic congestion, and increased transportation costs. These issues have economic implications, affecting trade, transportation of goods and services, and overall economic development of the local government (Ugwuoke *et al.*,2023; Anene *et al.*, 2023).

There are several types of plastic recycling systems, e.g., mechanical, chemical, plastic pyrolysis, and plastic-to-fuel (PTF) conversion, each designed to handle different types of plastic waste and recycling processes. These recycling methods have setbacks ranging from complex recycling processes, contamination issues, limited recycling infrastructure, environmental impacts of the recycling process (some recycling processes produce hazardous by-products or emissions, including greenhouse gases and volatile organic compounds, which contribute to air pollution if not properly controlled, raising environmental concerns), limited feedstock compatibility, high initial cost, complex technology to limited market demand (Saygin and Baysal, 2025; Pandey *et al.*, 2023 ;

Mwanza, 2021; Davidson *et al.*, 2021; Sambyal *et al.*, 2025; Tiwari *et al.*, 2023)

Many research works have been done in recent times in use of plastic waste in construction. Sau *et al.*, 2023 investigated the utilization of plastic waste (polyethylene (PE) and polyethylene-terephthalate (PET)) as replacement of natural aggregates in sustainable concrete. They observed that the presence of waste plastic affected some physical and chemical properties of the concrete.

Tladi *et al.*, 2023 worked on the Utilization of Plastic Waste and Waste Rubber Tyres to Modify Bitumen Binder in Road Construction. They showed that in bitumen-rubber tyre modified binder, increasing the rubber tyre percentage above 5% in the binder, resulted in low ductility, due to the elasticity property of rubber, for both 5.5% and 6% bitumen. They also observed that in the Bitumen-plastic modified binder, the softening point and ductility had a direct proportionality relationship. As the plastic percentage in the total weight of the binder increased, so did the ductility and the softening point.

Ali *et al.*, 2024 investigated the suitability of the high-density polyethylene (HDPE) wastes, for asphalt mixtures. They summed by saying that the High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE)

modified asphalt mixture gives more advantages compared to the traditional one, as plastic mixture significantly improved the mechanical properties and performance of asphalt mixture compared with traditional mixture

Kocak (2024) investigates the possible use of two common sustainable road construction materials, recycled asphalt pavement (RAP) and recycled tire rubber (RTR), for pavement maintenance applications. His results showed that any recycled hot-mix asphalt outperformed the cold mixtures (CM). He also observed that 100% hot RAP mixture with petroleum-based rejuvenator performed as well as any combined RTR-RAP mixtures.

Nasar *et al.*, 2024, reviewed the findings of previous studies in plastic modified asphalt focusing on the ideal blending ratios, mixing parameters, the physical, thermal, and rheological performance of waste plastic modified asphalt. The review article put forward details of various field projects across the globe utilizing waste plastic. The review concluded by presenting key findings, identifying research gaps, and suggesting future directions to advance the knowledge and to fully comprehend the possible application of waste plastic modified bitumen in sustainable road construction.

It is seen from the review that non of the studies specifically worked on the suitability of Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) for asphalt mixtures. Only a few experiments are reported on the use of Polyethylene (PE) and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) on concrete mixtures but not on asphalt mixtures. This proves the significance of a study to be conducted where PET waste plastic is used as partial replacement for bitumen in asphalt modification.

This study aimed at recycling waste plastic bottles without cap (Polyethylene Terephthalate) into a raw material for road construction, thereby mopping the environment of this plastic waste as well as lead to construction of cheaper (reduced asphalt cost) and more durable roads in Nigeria. Polyethylene Terephthalate was chosen for this study for the large volumes generated and its devastating environmental impacts in the area, and Nigeria in general (Dumbili, and Henderson, 2020; Olanrewaju and Oyebade, 2019; Khoaele *et al.*, 2023). Bitumen is the costliest road construction material (Siva and Naga, 2022; Kandhal *et al.*, 2023; Riekstins *et al.*, 2024; Ghoroghi, 2023). This study is also aimed at reducing the quantity of bitumen needed for road construction leading to a sustainable road infrastructure. This research therefor aimed to

address the major environmental and infrastructural problem of the area and the country at large (Adagunodo *et al.*, 2024; Auwalu and Bello, 2023; Anabaraonye *et al.*, 2023; Kehinde *et al.*, 2020).

With the extent of bad road in the area and the country at large (Akujor *et al.*, 2022; Adedeji *et al.*, 2023), there will be a huge market for waste Polyethylene Terephthalate by the road construction industry in the country. In no time, the demand for the plastic waste will surpass the supply and that will mop up this plastic waste in Nigeria, a good way of mitigating plastic pollution in the country.

Interestingly, this recycling method is devoid of all the challenges of the other plastic recycling methods.

Materials and Method

Waste Plastic Bottles

Waste plastic bottles were purchased from waste plastic vendors, garbage trucks and dump sites from Owerri West Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Aggregates

Coarse aggregates and stone dust were purchased from Akamkpa quarry in Cross

River state. River sand was taken from Etinan beach in Akwa Ibom state.

Bitumen

Grade 60/70 bitumen was purchased from Mobil Bitumen depot in Port-Harcourt, Rivers state.

Preparation of Waste plastic

The collected plastic wastes (Figure 1) were separated into bottles and caps. The bottles were gathered and washed with detergent to remove impurities, labels, and other contaminants. The washed plastic bottles were air dried for 24 hours (Figure 2) to ensure complete removal of water.

Figure 1 Plastic waste bottles

Figure 2 Cleaned and dried plastic bottles

Pulverisation of waste plastic

The cleaned plastic bottles were pulverised using a locally fabricated pulverising machine

(Figure 3) into small plastic flakes to facilitate improved mixing with bitumen. The waste passing the 2.36 IS sieve was used for the study.

Figure 3 Pulverising machine with the pulverised plastic flakes

Trial Mix Design (ASTM C 136)

In designing the asphalt, trial mix method was used. The aggregates used were crushed stone 5-15mm, 0-5mm and 0-2mm. The mix: 5-15 (34%), 0-5 (54%) and 0-2 (14%) entering the envelop as required by ASTM D6927 (2005) was adopted for the mix design.

Design of Traditional Asphalt (Control sample)

The traditional asphalt (asphalt without plastic addition) was designed with incremental addition (5.0%,5.5%,6.0%,6.5%,7.0% and 7.5%.) of 60/70 bitumen heated to a temperature of about 135°C to 4000g of

aggregates (crushed stone, filler and river sand.) heated up to 160°C in a mixer. The aggregates were selected in line with ASTM C 136 (2005) and ASTM 6927(2005). The mixture of bitumen and aggregates were properly mixed by the mixer. For each percentage of incremental bitumen, e.g. 5%, three samples weighing 1200g each were collected from the mixer and compacted to produce three cylindrical specimens for the Marshal test. The average result of each parameter for the three specimen was taken as the result for that percentage plastic addition. The compacted specimens were extruded after 24 hours (Figure 4), weighed in air and water,

for volume and bulk density calculations. The specimens were soaked in clean water for one hour and reweighed, for water absorption calculations. Thereafter, the samples were placed in a water bath at a temperature of 60° C for 30 minutes at intervals of 10 minutes to give room for testing one sample before another is ready for test. After 30 minutes in

the water bath, the samples were removed, cleaned, placed in the breaking head and tested with the Marshal machine for Stability and Flow. A total of eighteen (18) cylindrical specimens were compacted and tested. The traditional asphalt served as the control for the research.

Figure 4 Cylindrical test specimens

The following result were recorded from the Marshal tests:

- Bulk density
- Specific gravity of material
- Volume of aggregates
- Void in mineral aggregates
- Void in total mix
- Percentage void filled with bitumen
- Flow

- Stability

Calculation of Optimum Bitumen Content (OBC)

The OBC was calculated from the curves of Stability vs Bitumen Content (Figure 2). Bulk Density vs Bitumen Content (Figure 3) Voids in Total Mix vs Bitumen Content (Figure 4) and Voids Filled with Bitumen vs Bitumen

Content (Figure 5) plotted from the Marshal test results of the traditional specimens. Stability was read directly from the marshal machine. Void in total mix was calculated with Equation 1,

$$VTM = 100 - \frac{100I}{J} \quad 1$$

Where: VTM = Void in Total Mix

I = Bulk density of compacted specimen

J = Specific gravity of the specimen

Also, Voids filled with bitumen was calculated using Equation 2,

$$VFB = 100 * \frac{K}{M} \quad 2$$

Where: $K = \frac{D+I}{SG BIT} \quad 3$

Where: D = Bitumen content

SG BIT = Specific gravity of Bitumen

$$M = 100 - L \quad 4$$

Where $L = \frac{(100-D)I}{SG AGG} \quad 5$

Where: SG AGG = Specific gravity of Aggregate

PET modified Asphalt

The procedure of designing traditional asphalt was repeated with the addition of PET to the asphalt mix. PET contents of 6%,8%,10%,12% and 14% by weight of the Optimum bitumen content (OBC) were used to partially replace bitumen in the mix through dry process. The plastic was added after the fractional bitumen (OBC minus the augmented percentage of plastic) was properly mixed with aggregates and the entire mixture thoroughly mixed. Three sets of cylindrical specimens were prepared and tested for each percent of plastic mix.

Data analysis

Descriptive analysis (mean and standard deviation) was used in analyzing the data.

Results and Discussion

Marshal Test Result

Traditional Asphalt: The Marshal test result for the traditional asphalt is presented in Table 1. 6.0%, 6.5% and 7.0 % bitumen addition

made the requirement for Voids in Total Mix. Only 6.5 and 7.0% bitumen addition made the requirement for Voids Filled with Bitumen. Apart from 5.0% bitumen addition, the others

met the criteria for Stability. The reference standards used are ASTM D 6927 (2005) FGN (1997) and FMWHM (2013).

Table 1 Marshal test result for the Traditional Asphalt

Bitumen Content (%)	Unit weight	VTM	VFB	Flow	Stability
5	2.28	8.8	53.55	1.9	2.79
5.5	2.31	6.85	61.46	2.1	4.63
6	2.36	4.47	71.69	2.21	7.66
6.5	2.36	3.67	77.44	2.37	8.62
7	2.35	3.29	79.48	2.41	9.79
7.5	2.35	2.49	83.14	2.47	9.41
SPECIFICATION		3 - 5%	75-82%	2 - 4mm	\geq 3.5

Optimum Bitumen Content (ASTM D6976-05)

Curves of Stability vs Bitumen Content, Bulk density vs Bitumen Content, and Voids in Total Mix vs Bitumen Content were plotted from Table 2, as shown in Figures 5 to 7. From the figure 5, bitumen content corresponding to maximum Stability = 7.0%. Figure 6 shows bitumen content corresponding to Maximum Bulk Density as

6%. While figure 7 shows 6.2 % Bitumen Content correspond to 4% Air Void in Total Mix. Flow corresponding to 6.4% bitumen content as seen from Figure 8 is 2.35mm. Figure 9 shows Voids Filled with Bitumen as 78%.

OBC was calculated from Equation 6,

$$OBC = \frac{7+6+6.2}{3} = 6.4\% \quad 6$$

Figure 5 Stability vs Bitumen Content

Figure 6 Bulk density vs Bitumen Content

Figure 7 % Voids in Total Mix vs Bitumen Content

Figure 8 Flow v Bitumen Content

Figure 9 Voids filled vs Bitumen Content

OBC Properties

Table 2 shows the properties of the designed (traditional) asphalt vis-a-vis the wearing course specification. The asphalt met all the

requirements for wearing course (ASTM D6927, 2005; FGN, 1997; FMWHM, 2013, Saleh *et al.*, 2023; Rangan *et al.*, 2023; Belayali *et al.*, 2023; Chen and Bahia.,2022).

Table 2 Marshal properties of OBC of the designed asphalt vis-a-vis Wearing Course Specification

Properties	OBC	Specification
Bitumen Content (%)	6.4	6-8%
Stability	9.2	≥ 3.5
Flow	2.4	2mm - 4mm
% Void in Total Mix	3.4	3 - 5%
% Void Filled with Bitumen	78	75 - 82%

PET modified Asphalt: The parameters of plastic modified asphalt by partial replacement of OBC by PET is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Properties of PET modified asphalt

Property	@OBC	94% OBC + 6% PET	92% OBC + 8% PET	90% OBC + 10% PET	88% OBC + 12% PET	86% OBC + 14% PET	Specification
Stability	9.2	3.9	6.3	6.7	10.8	7.1	≥ 3.5
Flow	2.40	1.35	1.81	1.68	2.27	1.64	2mm - 4mm
Void In Total Mix	3.40	4.90	4.47	4.88	4.45	5.67	3 - 5%
% Void Filled	78.00	70.80	72.97	70.27	77.54	66.54	75 - 82%

All the percentage replacement met the requirement for stability but fall short of flow requirement except 12% replacement.

All the percentage replacement met the requirements for percentage void in total mix except 14% replacement. Again, all the percentage replacement fell short of the requirements for percentage void filled with bitumen except 12% replacement. 12% PET replacement of OBC (Column 5) is the only replacement percentage that met all the requirement for wearing course asphalt. It also has the highest stability value, surpassing even that of the OBC. Hence, 12% replacement is the Optimum Plastic Content (OPC) for PET.

Chegenizadeh *et al.*, 2021 while studying the effect of Ethylene propylene diene monomer (EPDM) on asphalt performance had 2 to 4 % as Optimum Plastic Content (OPC). Faramarzi, *et al.*, 2013 in their study on the

effects of CNTs on hot mix asphalt marshal-parameters had stability values ranging from 1343 - 1780kg, effective gravity values of 2.32 - 2.33 (g/cm³) and flow values of between 3.05 and 3.33mm. Their flow results partly support the result of this work. On the other hand, Raza and Khan (2021) in their work on the influence of Marble Dust Filler on Marshal Properties of Hot Mix Asphalt, obtained stability values ranging from 1256kg - 1115kg, flow values of 9.03 - 9.60 mm and Bulk Specific gravity of 2.361 - 2.371g/cm³. Their flow values are at variant with the values gotten in this research and of course above the standards (2mm - 4mm). Caroles *et al.*, (2021) in using Peralite as a modifier observed stability values of 702.42 - 805.88kg. with flow values of 3.07 - 3.80 mm. They also got VTM values of 4.52 - 2.41% and VFB values of 76.29 - 89.04 %. Their results are in line with the results of this work.

Conclusion

In this study, the properties of bituminous mix when bitumen is partially replaced with pulverised PET plastic wastes was investigated. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) showed to be suitable for utilization as a partial replacement of bitumen for asphalt production at 12% replacement. Hence, 12% replacement is the Optimum Plastic Content (OPC) for PET. Nigeria is not yet in the list of countries where this technology is being practiced. Road construction companies in Nigeria are encouraged to adopt the result of this study to help in the construction of eco-friendly roads and maintenance applications in the country, while at the same time help in plastic waste management. This work no doubt will open the window for more research in this direction for sustainable plastic waste management and construction of cheaper and durable roads in Nigeria.

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